

"AGE AND RELEASING OF MINORS FROM LIABILITY AND PUNISHMENT"

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the consideration of the features of age in criminal liability and punishment of minors. The authors analyze the provisions of the criminal law, reflecting the specifics of the application of measures of criminal law coercion against minors. As a result of the study, it was concluded that the minor age of the person who committed the crime significantly reduces the limits of criminal liability, while allowing to apply special types of exemption from criminal liability and punishment to the guilty person.

In a state of law, the interests of the younger generation, the problems of its protection and normal development are in the first place, therefore a significant number of criminal legislations is aimed at protecting the rights of minors [1, p. 155]. Since gaining state independence, one of the first international documents that the Republic of Uzbekistan joined after the adoption of the Constitution is the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which was ratified in accordance with the resolution of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 1992. According to the Convention, every person under the age of 18 is a child. However, there is an exception to the general rule: if national legislation establishes an earlier age of majority, a person ceases to be considered a child until the age of 18 [2].

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not disclose the concept of the term "minor". However, Article 3 of the Law "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" provides the following definition of the concept: "A minor is a person who has not reached the age of eighteen years". This Law was adopted on September 29, 2010 to improve the effectiveness of preventing antisocial behavior, which introduced a judicial procedure for placing minors who are in a socially dangerous situation in specialized educational institutions and centers for social and legal assistance to minors.

It should be noted that for many years legal scholars have been trying to determine the optimal age of criminal responsibility, i.e., the age at which a person must bear criminal responsibility, realizing his guilt. Various grounds were

proposed in accordance with which the gradation of the age of criminal responsibility took place depending on the severity of the crimes committed. Age is an indicator of a person's social maturity and his ability to give a correct assessment of social phenomena. For a person who has committed a crime, it is necessary not only to understand the social danger of the deed, its awareness and assessment, but also the ability to manage the appropriate behavior and "foresee the consequences, create their mental model" [3, p. 134-135].

In a systematic analysis of the age of criminal responsibility of minors, we consider it appropriate to consider also the norms of international law. Under article 40(3) of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, States parties are encouraged to set a minimum age below which it is implied that children at that age do not have the capacity to violate criminal law.

There are different opinions about the unambiguous age of criminal responsibility. There are no categorical international standards in this matter. In General Comment No. 10, the Committee on the Rights of the Child concludes that "a minimum age of criminal responsibility below 12 years of age is considered by the Committee to be not internationally acceptable" [4].

At the same time, the Committee emphasizes that States parties should not lower the minimum age below 12 if the age is set above that age. States parties are also strongly encouraged to increase the minimum age of criminal responsibility, for example to 14 or 16 years. Of course, nothing prevents participating countries from setting a minimum age of 18 years. A number of countries, including Brazil, have already done so [5].

Guidance on this matter is also reflected in Article 4 of the Beijing Rules, which recommends that the lower age of criminal responsibility "should not be set too low, taking into account aspects of emotional, spiritual and intellectual maturity" [6].

The Committee on the Rights of the Child clearly states that children who are above the minimum age of criminal responsibility and who are in conflict with the law should be held less liable than adults because "children differ from adults in their physical and psychological development and in their emotional and educational needs" [7].

In setting the age of criminal responsibility, we must take into account that a child below the age of criminal responsibility does not have the capacity to commit a crime. This means that such children are immune from criminal prosecution – they cannot be prosecuted by the authorities, nor can they be subject to criminal law procedures and measures. An important element of the institution of the minimum age of criminal responsibility is that in order to be responsible for their actions, the child must reach emotional, spiritual and intellectual maturity. The minimum age in different countries is defined at significantly different levels - from six years to eighteen years. On average, this age is determined at the level of twelve years [8].

In our country, only sane individuals who have reached the age established by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan are subject to criminal liability. As a general rule, for the vast majority of crimes, criminal liability begins at the age of 16. Only for some of the offenses

specified in article 17 of the Criminal Code, it occurs from 13, 14 or 18 years.

If we consider in more detail the age of criminal responsibility under the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, then persons who were thirteen years old before committing a crime are liable only for premeditated murder under aggravating circumstances (part two of Article 97 of the Criminal Code).

Adolescents who have reached the age of 14 can be brought to it: for premeditated murder, intentional grievous bodily injury, intentional moderate bodily injury, rape, kidnapping, robbery, extortion, robbery, theft and for some other crimes. Cases of bringing to criminal liability only after reaching 18 years of age include: evading the maintenance of minors or disabled persons; evasion from the maintenance of parents; involvement of a minor in antisocial behavior; official forgery; receiving a bribe and some other crimes.

Responsibility of persons who have committed a crime under the age of eighteen comes in accordance with the general provisions and taking into account the specifics provided for in section six of the General Part of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [8].

Further, I would like to draw attention to the age of criminal responsibility in foreign countries, thus, in the legislation of the countries of the Romano-Germanic legal family, the minimum age of criminal responsibility is fixed: in Belgium - from 18 years old, in Poland - from 15 years old, in Germany, Russia and Austria - from the age of 14, in Portugal and the Netherlands - from the age of 12 (however, there is practically no

criminal liability from this age). In the countries of the Anglo-Saxon legal family, the age of criminal responsibility is defined a little lower, namely, in Ireland it is 7 years, in Scotland - 8, in England - 10.

It should be noted that in all these countries, adolescents sentenced to a real term do not serve it in a general prison, but in a special correctional institution, where usually a less harsh regime and repressive measures are taken in the most extreme cases [9].

We also note that when determining the age of a person, the judicial and investigative authorities need to take into account that a person is considered to have reached a certain age "not on the day of birth, but after the expiration of the day on which this day falls, i.e., from zero o'clock the next day [11].

In cases where the age of a person is established not according to the relevant documents (passport, birth certificate, etc.), but on the basis of the conclusion of a forensic medical examination in years, then the last day of the year named by the experts is considered his birthday, and when determining the age by the minimum and maximum number of years, the court should proceed from the minimum age of such a person assumed by the experts [10].

Thus, based on the above ages of criminal responsibility, we can state that in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the legislator establishes a general age of criminal responsibility and a lower one, when responsibility for a certain range of offenses specified in Article 17 of the Criminal Code comes earlier.

We especially note that the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan differentiates the age at which a minor can be recognized as the subject of a crime,

directly pointing to four age characteristics of the subject. The minimum age established by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not violate the norms of international law. However, we consider it expedient to raise the age of criminal responsibility to 14 years. Considering that in criminal science a minor is a special subject of a crime. Compared with adults, minors are not fully developed in terms of physical, psychological and physiological indicators. Therefore, their level of awareness of social

problems is limited. They are easily involved, incited to commit offenses, including crimes. However, the characteristics of mental instability are at the same time more favorable conditions for the re-education and education of minors than adult offenders. Therefore, the release of minors from criminal liability is provided not only by the general rules for exemption from criminal liability, but by special rules applicable only to a person under the age of eighteen.

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6. Article 228 of the Brazilian Constitution states that "persons under the age of eighteen cannot be subject to criminal prosecution and are subject to the rules of special legislation".
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